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Develop English Electronic Module for Tourism Through Analysis of Learner's and Context

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Abstract

Tourism development in Lampung province has been developing rapidly and the need for English communication skills at the tourism workplace is highly required due to a lot of visitors are foreigners. The state Polytechnic of Lampung has opened a new program study of tour and travel to support the government in the tourism sector and train students to have better English skills therefore need to develop good materials for teaching which meet with tourism industry. Developing good English materials for tourism based on an Android smartphone is needed since students lack academic hours for learning English. The objective of this research is to develop an electronic module (e-module) of English for tourism based on analysis learners and context that become important step in Dick and Carey Model. The development of e-module of English for tourism applied collaboration of research and development (R&D) that focus on the third of ten steps of Dick and Carey Model. The result of this research is a prototype of e-module of English for tourism that has been validated and published on google play store.

Keywords: E-Module, English for Tourism, Learners' Analysis

1. Introduction

ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) policy was applied in 2015, cooperation between ASEAN countries in trading will be expanded in services and products. Communication and adaptability are very important and the main keys for the running well of cooperation. Building cooperation among ASEAN countries could have a problem if the stake holders do not competent in foreign language communication. The barrier to foreign languages, especially English, is a challenge for Indonesia in the MEA. The ASEAN Study Center stated that the quality of Indonesian skilled or professional workers, the use of English is only around 44%, 36% computer use, 30% fast learning ability, 33% thinking skills and 13% basic skills (Keliat, 2013). One of the things that are urgent to become a priority in the development of every individual and organization of business actors is the mastery of foreign languages, especially English. Mastery of foreign languages such as English and Arabic is very important to access religious and business knowledge (Muhammad, 2014). Students who did internships at multinational companies in the ASEAN region experience problems in English, especially in speaking and listening skills, while reading and writing skills are rarely used in work apprenticeships. Students from Asian countries generally have difficulty speaking English in speaking and writing during education due to differences in learning styles, culture, and other social problems. Even though English language skills are needed when working in the global tourism industry.

The global tourism industry is growing rapidly and opening big workplaces in Indonesia, especially in provinces that have great tourism potential. Lampung Province as the main gateway to the island of Sumatra has very good tourism potential, especially data on natural tourist attractions. Based on data released by the Lampung provincial tourism office, it shows that from January to June 2019 there were 100,469 foreign tourists visiting Lampung province and more than four million domestic tourists, namely 4,525,127. The increase in tourist visits in Lampung province was 17.07 percent compared to 2017 (Ikhwan & Qodratul Ikhwan, 2019). This has caused the tourism industry in Lampung province to grow better. The tourism industry plays an important role in Lampung province because it is one of the mainstays of Lampung's income sector. The development of the tourism industry makes English communication skills even more important. Employees who work in the tourism sector must be able to communicate with foreigners using a foreign language such as English. Based on the results of interviews with regional administrators of the Indonesian Tour Guides Association (DPD HPI) Lampung, it shows that the English language skills of tourism guides are still lacking, especially speaking, reading and writing skills and the TOEIC score is still below the SKKNI standard for competence. English. Tour guides who have good English skills will provide comfort for foreign tourists and will have a positive impact on all things in the tourism industry sector (Erazo et al., 2019).

The global tourism industry is growing rapidly and opening big workplaces in Indonesia, especially in provinces that have a big tourism potential. Lampung Province as the main gateway of Sumatra island has very good tourism potential, especially in natural tourist attractions. Based on data released by the Lampung provincial tourism office, it show that from January to June 2019 there were 100,469 foreign tourists visiting Lampung province and more than four million domestic tourists about 4,525,127. The increase in tourist visits in Lampung province was 17.07 percent compared to 2017 (Ikhwan & Qodratul Ikhwan, 2019). As a result the tourism industry in Lampung province grow much better. The tourism industry plays an important role in Lampung province because it is one of the mainstays sector of Lampung's income. The development of the tourism industry makes English communication skills more important. Employees who work in the tourism sector must be able to communicate with foreigners using a foreign language such as English. Based on the results of interviews with regional administrators of the Indonesian Tour Guides Association (DPD HPI) Lampung, it could be concluded that the English language skills of tourism guides are lack of English skills, especially speaking, reading and writing skills and the TOEIC score is also still below the SKKNI standard for English competency. Tour guides who have good English skills will provide comfort for foreign tourists and will have a positive impact to all things in the sector of tourism industry (Erazo et al., 2019).

The Minister of Manpower and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia has made a decision in the tourism sector in the tour and travel sub-sector Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI: 2004) that English communication competence are speaking, reading and writing at the level of basic work skills, proficiency intermediate work and advanced work skills. The tourism sector requires English skills; speaking (100%), listening (75%), writing (25%), and reading (25%) and facing several problems such as lack of training for hotels and tourism, not actively working with the tourism industry to strengthen the business network of all tourism stakeholders, lack of practice in reading and explaining tourism city maps, and difficulty understanding English accents such as English speakers from China, Japan, India (Puspitasari, 2018).

World Bank data shows that the Indonesian quality of skills and professional workers having competence in English communication skills is 44%, computer skills 36%, learning abilities 30% faster, thinking skills 33% and basic skills 13% (Maskur, 2016). In addition, the Ministry of Manpower and Manpower noted that Indonesia's obstacle in the ASEAN Economic Community was English communication. The results of the EPI (English Proficiency index) survey in 2018 were held in 88 countries, Indonesia was ranked 51st out of 88 countries and ranked 13th out of 21 Asian countries. Indonesia remained from 2017 in the low proficiency category with a score of 51.58 (low proficiency). Meanwhile, Singapore is in fifth place with a score of 68.63 (very high proficiency), Malaysia is in 13th place with a score of 58.32 (high proficiency) and the Philippines is in 15th place with a score of 61.84 (high proficiency). These data show that Indonesia is left behind in English skills compared to other countries in ASEAN (EF EPI, 2018).

State Polytechnic of Lampung (Polinela) as a vocational higher education needs to prepare its graduates in the field of knowledge studied and the ability to communicate in foreign languages, especially English. Communication skills

are very important in the 21st century learning era (21st century learning; 4C: collaboration, Communication, Creative, and Critical Thinking). Polytechnic is a vocational higher education that aims to prepare students to get a job with certain applied skills to the maximum equivalent of an undergraduate program (S1). Polinela's curriculum has provided learning English 1, 2 and 3 courses for students in all study programs. Unfortunately, implementation has not made a significant contribution to improving students' English communication skills. The results of the TOEIC (English Language Test for International Communication) test conducted by ETS (Educational Testing Service) in 2018 showed that on average 329, students' English communication skills were categorized at the basic level (average score 329). There are five students (1%) at the level of basic work proficiency (score 605-780), at the intermediate level or elementary proficiency plus (score 405-600) as many as 155 students (25%), at the elementary level or elementary proficiency (scores of 255-400) totaled 311 students (51%), and at the beginner level or basic proficiency (scores 5-250) there were 138 students (23%). It can be concluded that in general, students' skills in English communication are very low.

The learning outcomes of students in the first semester of the 2017/2018 school year for English courses can be categorized as quite good where out of a total of 537 students, 219 students (40.8%) scored A (40.8%), B's 208 people (38.7%) and a C value of 110 people (20.5%). Although the first semester's English scores can be said to be quite good, the initial test results of students' English proficiency using the TOEIC average have low abilities with a score of 255 - 400 or Elementary (55.7%) and a score of 5-250 or Novice (35%). The initial TOEIC test results specifically for travel students also show that the students' English language skills are still very low with an average score of 280. The English skills of students (53 students) in the travel study program are at the basic level or basic proficiency (46%) and at the elementary or elementary proficiency (48%).

Based on the results of observations by researcher that the English tourism material delivered by the lecturer used English text books and in the form of a compilation of material packaged in practical learning modules which compiled by the lecturer. Tourism English learning material in the first semester focuses more on grammar based or provides a lot of grammar training and activities are mostly centered on the teacher not on students (student center) so that it does not provide opportunities for students to practice language (language exposes) in online class between students (pair practice) and lecturers. Learning English obstacles in tourism experienced by students while learning English according to Polinela's lecturers, among others, feeling of shame, fear of speaking English wrongly, lack of confidence, less motivated and lack of vocabularies.

The results of observations by researcher show that independent tourism English learning resources (modules, handouts and web learning) are very limited. The problem of the availability of independent learning resources is a priority to be resolved considering that there are very few opportunities to practice tourism English outside the classroom or on the Polinela campus. Another problem in learning English for tourism in the Tourism Travel Study Program in Polinela is the lack of opportunities for students to practice their English skills. Common problems in learning a foreign language include the lack of opportunities to use foreign languages by teachers and students in their environment (Roblyer, Margareth D and Doering, 2010). One way to solve this problem is the need to develop independent learning materials based on student analysis and analysis of tourism stakeholders (context). Tourism English electronic module material can be accessed anytime and anywhere. Independent learning materials such as electronic modules are expected to help improve students' English competency.

The development of an electronic module (e-module) for English learning materials needs to consider student's needs and the needs of graduate users, namely tourism stakeholders. Electronic module development also requires creativity, productive thinking habits, creating active, effective, innovative and pleasant conditions. Lecturers should develop their own multimedia applications so that they can contribute effectively in solving some learning problems (Babiker, 2015). Material development should be based on the analysis of students and tourism stakeholders (Dick, W. & Carey, 2015). English in tourism according to the Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI) issued by the Ministry of Manpower in the tourism sector in the tourism travel agency sub-sector (No. Kep 238 / MEN / X / 2004) is divided into three categories, namely basic, intermediate operational competences. and high. The three competencies in tourism English include speaking, reading and writing skills.

Based on the description of the importance of intervening in learning conditions both internally and externally so that the learning process is optimal, it is necessary to develop e-modules for learning English for tourism based on the analysis of Learners and Context at the Lampung State Polytechnic as an alternative source of supplementary learning materials. It can provide a solution for improving the competencies of English tourism for students.

2. Method

Developing electronic modules of English for tourism through analysis of learners and context is research and development (R &D). R and D has purposed to develop and improve the quality of instruction. It used mix method that presented the data analysis of qualitative and quantitative. Research on developing English for tourism e-module through analysis leaners and context using the third steps of the Dick and Carey Model design that is analysis learners and contexts.

The study of developing e-module for English for tourism was based on analysis of learners and context. The analysis of learners was conducted by having questioners to students of Polinela at tourism study program and stake holder of tourism industries in Lampung province. The questioner has distributed online through google form. It is used to know learners entry behaviour, English level, students motivation in learning English for tourism. While the context analysis has been conducted by gathering some information from stake holders from tourism sectors using questioner and observation. The participants were students of tour and travel study program of Politeknik Negeri Lampung and tourism stake holders of Lampung province including association of tourism destination (PUTRI), guide (HPI), tour and travels (ASITA), hotels (PHRI) and also local governments. The purposive random sampling was used as the sampling technique in this study. There were 136 students involved in the study and 158 from tourism stake holders of Lampung province.

This study used two methods to collect data; questioner and library study. Questioners are instruments that used to get information from respondents both students and stake holders, while library study was used to obtain relevant theories to make instruments of research in the form of questioners and used for analyzing the needs. The data analysis method that had been used in the study was descriptive method. It was used to describe and analyze the of learners and contexts or stake holders of English of tourism. The results of this analysis used to develop teaching materials that is electronic module (e-module) for English for tourism.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the result of analyzing data that has been collected, the students responds from the questioners classified into three language skills based on Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI) issued by the Ministry of Manpower in the tourism sector in the tourism travel agency sub-sector (No. Kep 238 / MEN / X / 2004 including; 1) speaking, 2) reading and 3) writing and students perception about the role of English in tourism work place.

1. Student's ability in speaking

The student's competences in English speaking skills have been identified based on the result of the questioners analysis. Questioners cover three aspects of speaking abilities communicate in spoken English with tourists and colleagues, understanding and using polite and friendly sentences verbally both formal and informal, and speaking by telephone. The following table indicates the results of students competences in speaking skills related to English for tourism in workplace.

Table 1: Student's speaking competences in speaking skills

No.	Tourism English competency (SKKNI)	Very Bad	Enough	Good	Very Good
1	My ability to communicate in spoken English with tourists and colleagues on matters related to basic and daily activities at work and tourist service activities		59,6%	34,6%	
2	My ability to understand and use polite and friendly sentences verbally and know when to use formal or informal sentences in English.	5,9%	43,4%	48,5%	
3	My ability to speak by telephone (greeting, leaving a message, asking apology, and offering helps) in English.	3,7%	43,4%	50,0%	2,9%

The table showed if the student's speaking skills related to communication with tourists and colleague dealing with basic and daily activities at work and tourist service activities were enough while understanding and using polite and friendly sentences verbally and know when to use formal or informal was as good as speaking by telephone.

2. Student's ability in reading

The second analysis was the reading competences based on Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI) issued by the Ministry of Manpower in the tourism sector in the tourism travel agency sub-sector (No. Kep 238 / MEN / X / 2004) is as follow;

Table 2: Student's competences in reading skills

No	Tourism English competency (SKKNI)	Very Bad	Enough	Good	Very Good
1	My ability to read the general signs (signate, logo / image, and signs) of the tourism industry in English	5,1%	46,3%	43,4%	5,1%
2	My ability to read work documents (brochures, leaflets, memos, e mails and facsimiles) in English in tourism.	5,1%	41,2%	45,6%	8,1%
3	My ability to read and understand work instructions and work procedures in English (guidance module, memos, e-mails, and leaflets / brochures).	4,4%	44,1%	47,8%	3,7%
4	Ability to read charts / charts / graphs in English (tourism trend graphs, reports, etc.)	6,6%	61,8%	29,4%	2,2%

From the result of the student's reading ability dealing with English for tourism in table above, it can be seen that students competences in reading the general signs of the tourism industry in English were enough, for reading work documents was as good as reading and understanding work instructions and work procedures, while ability in reading charts was enough.

3. Student's ability in writing

There are three competences in writing which considered as standard of Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI) in tourism work place that stated in questioners, they are; ability to write message, ability to complete or fill out form and write basic and every day documents at work place. The result analysis toward student's skills in writing ability are shown as follow:

Table 3: Student's competences in writing skills

No	Tourism English competency (SKKNI)	Very Bad	Enough	Good	Very Good
1	My ability to write messages, instructions, identity in English when receiving a telephone.	3,7%	46,3%	44,1%	5,9%
2	My ability to complete or fill out forms in English (registration form, travel schedule form, insurance claim form, passport form, visa form, report form, map form and graphics).	2,9%	43,4%	47,1%	6,6%
3	My ability to write basic and everyday documents in English at work (leaflets, messages, correspondence, memos, e-mails, simple instructions / procedures, customer instructions etc.)	9,6%	52,9%	35,3%	2,2%

Based on the result of analysis on student's writing skill indicate that the student's competences in writing messages, instructions, identity in English when receiving a telephone was as enough as writing in basic and everyday documents in English at work. While the competences in completing or filling out forms were good.

4. Student's opinion about the role of English in tourism

The results of the questionnaire showed that students think about mastering English for tourism is very important 57.4% and important 21.3% and quite important 21.3%. Students believe mastering tourism English can improve my future career in the world of work very confident 77.2% and 14.7% confident. Students want to improve their tourism English skills on speaking skills of 94.9%, listening 46.3%, reading 32.4% and writing 36%.

Based on the result of analyzing data of the context analysis or tourism industry stakeholders that have been collected from the stake holders which involved the association of tourism destinations (PUTRI), guides (HPI), tours and travels (ASITA), hotels (PHRI) and also local governments also classified into three language skills based on Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI) issued by the Ministry of Manpower in the tourism sector in the tourism travel agency sub-sector (No. Kep 238 / MEN / X / 2004 including; 1) speaking, 2) reading and 3) writing.

1. Stake holder's ability in speaking

The stake holder's competences in English speaking skills have been identified based on the result of the questioners analysis. Questioners cover three aspects of speaking abilities communicate in spoken English with tourists and colleagues, understanding and using polite and friendly sentences verbally both formal and informal, and speaking by telephone. The following table indicates the results of stake holder's competences in speaking skills related to English for tourism in workplace.

Table 4: Stake holder's competences in writing skills

No	Tourism English competency (SKKNI)	Very Bad	Enough	Good	Very Good
1	My ability to communicate in spoken English with tourists and colleagues on matters related to basic and daily activities at work and tourist service activities	3,6%	26,6%	43,7%	23,4%
2	My ability to understand and use polite and friendly sentences verbally and know when to use formal (formal) or informal (informal) sentences in English.	3,8%	24,1%	41,1%	31,0%
3	My ability to speak by telephone (greeting, leaving a message, asking apology, and offering helps) in English.	3,8%	26,6%	38,0%	31,6%

The table showed if the stake holder's speaking skills related to communication with tourist and colleague dealing with basic and daily activities at work and tourist service activities, understanding and using polite and friendly sentences verbally and know when to use formal or informal and speaking by telephone were good.

2. Stake holder's ability in reading

The second analysis regarding to the reading competences of stake holders covered about reading the general signs of the tourism industry in English, reading work documents and reading and understanding work instructions and work procedures, while ability in reading charts was enough. The results of the analysis as follow;

Table 5: Stake holder's competences in reading skills

No	Tourism English competency (SKKNI)	Very Bad	Enough	Good	Very Good
1	My ability to read the general signs (signate, logo / image, and signs) of the tourism industry in English	6,3%	29,1%	34,8%	29,7%
2	My ability to read work documents (brochures, leaflets, memos, e-mails and facsimiles) in English in tourism.	2,5%	30,4%	39,9%	27,2%
3	My ability to read and understand work instructions and work procedures in English (guidance module, memos, e-mails, and leaflets / brochures).	3,8%	27,2%	43,7%	25,3%
4	Ability to read charts / charts / graphs in English (tourism trend graphs, reports, etc.)	6,3%	39,9%	38,0%	15,8%

From the result of the stake holder's reading ability in English for tourism in table above, it can be seen that students competences in reading the general signs of the tourism industry in English were good, for reading work documents was also as good as read and understand work instructions and work procedures, while ability in reading charts was also good.

3. Stake holder's ability in writing

There are three competences in writing which are considered as standard of Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI) in tourism work place that stated in questioners, they are; ability to write message, ability to complete or fill out form and write basic and every day documents at work place. The result analysis toward stake holder's skills in writing ability are shown as follow:

Table 5: Stake holder's competences in reading skills

No	Tourism English competency (SKKNI)	Very Bad	Enough	Good	Very Good
1	My ability to write messages, instructions, identity in English when receiving a telephone.	5,1%	27,8%	38,6%	28,5%
2	My ability to complete or fill out forms in English (registration form, travel schedule form, insurance claim form, passport form, visa form, report form, map form and graphics).	4,4%	25,3%	46,2%	24,1%
3	My ability to write basic and everyday documents in English at work (leaflets, messages, correspondence, memos, e-mails, simple instructions / procedures, customer instructions etc.)	7,0%	27,2%	41,8%	24,1%

Based on the result of analysis on stake holder's writing skill indicated that the stake holder's competences in writing messages, instructions, identity in English when receiving a telephone were as good as writing in basic and everyday documents in English at work. While the competences in completing or filling out forms were good.

4. Stake holder's opinion about the role of English in tourism

The results of the questionnaire indicate that stake holder think that mastering English for tourism is very important and can improve my future career in the world of their work. Stake holders also want to improve their tourism English skills on speaking, listening, reading and writing.

Regarding to the result of the analysis of learners and context indicated that student's competences in English for tourism mostly were enough while stake holder's competences were good, therefore it can be a consideration in developing electronic module of English for tourism. The result of the analysis of learners and context could be as recommendation in structuring e-module of English for tourism especially about the difficulty of the lessons and topics in the e-module. As results the developing of e-module will be more communicative and meets with student's and stake holder's needs.

Developing e-module of English communication skills for tourism are suggested to include; general language skills namely speaking, listening, reading and writing (Man & Leong, 2011), (Prachanant, 2012), (Chaudhary & Kaur, 2016) and special English skills in the tourism workplace such as; writing and sending e-mails and faxes, making tickets online, surfing the internet, making online hotel reservations and offering destination guides (Zahedpisheh et al., 2017), complex written documents such as letters or budgets, telephone conversations, making presentations to audiences, attending exhibitions and conferences and understanding all types of written information about tourist destinations (Zahedpisheh et al., 2017). Tourism industry workers must be able to communicate English in several tourism services with English topics such as; greetings, facial expressions and body movements (non-verbal communication), cross-cultural understanding, types of accommodation, hotel facilities, staffing and internal organization, reservation and check-in, hotel and restaurant services, phone calls, complaints and solutions, describing tourism skills objects, tour guides and presentations (Puspitasari, 2018).

Basic English skills in tourism, especially hospitality, they are; how to greet guests, provide necessary information, respond to questions and requests, use prompts, body language, resolve customer difficulties, and respond to complaints well (Blue & Harun, 2003). Khalida (2020) adds that the need for tourism English language skills needed as human resources in the tourism sector in hotels, among others; greeting, giving directions, meetings, presentations, handling complaints, offering laundry services (offering laundry services), tourism places, travel plans and schedules (tourism plans and schedules), room facilities, and hotel services and facilities (Khalida, 2019).

English for tourism and hospitality has been categorized in English for special purposes (ESP) and is very important and essential in all professional fields especially in the tourism and hospitality industry due to its specific nature and concept (Zahedpisheh et al., 2017). English communication is an essential element of the hospitality industry. Excellent speaking skills and written communication skills are highly rated as important skills for hospitality practitioners in various places (Bobanovic, 2011). The study of English for tourism shows that students and employees in the tourism and hospitality sector experience English communication skills problems in their workplace. The English problems faced by tourism sector workers in general are; oral communication (speaking) (Gani & Damayanti, 2018), listening (reading), writing (writing) and reading (Al-khatib, 2005), inability to understand foreign accents or accents, words (words) and inappropriate expressions, inadequate vocabularies, and a lack of grammar knowledge (Prachanant, 2012). Problems related to English for tourism are the quality of lecturers, English subjects in the tourism curriculum, teaching materials, student opportunities to communicate in English and the assessment process (Khoung et al., 2017).

English proficiency according to the Indonesian National Work Competency Standards (SKKNI) issued by the Ministry of Manpower in the tourism sector in the tourism travel agency sub-sector (Kep. 238 / MEN / X / 2004) is divided into three categories, namely basic, intermediate and high. Basic operational level English competency units, namely;

- 1) The skills and attitudes required by travel and tourism industry employees dealing with English-speaking customers and colleagues in order to be able to communicate orally at a basic operational level. This includes basic and daily conversations, such as welcoming guests, giving goodbye and serving guests both face-to-face and by telephone, while for intermediate it includes speaking and listening skills about routine and non-routine matters, serving customers, negotiating and maintaining customer relationships with respect to the appropriate level of responsibility of the employee concerned. The high level includes effective and fluent oral communication and is able to negotiate and provide complete information, but is not intended to reflect the skills of a professional translator.

2) The skills and attitudes required by travel and tourism industry employees dealing with English-speaking customers and colleagues to read in English at an operational level. This includes basic daily activities such as reading basic reports, e-mails, facsimiles, letters, diagrams and brochures and recognizing common signs. Meanwhile, the middle level includes routine and non-routine activities such as reading reports, e-mails, facsimiles, letters, diagrams and brochures. The high level includes the ability to read a number of complex working documents and, if required, provide informal translations and summaries at a high level of complexity and fluency. However this is not intended to reflect the skills of a professional translator.

3) The skills and attitudes required by tourism and travel industry employees dealing with English-speaking customers and colleagues to write in English at the basic operational level in the workplace. This includes basic everyday activities such as writing basic reports. E-mail, facsimile, letters and diagramming. Meanwhile, at the middle level, it includes routine and non-routine activities such as writing reports, e-mails, facsimiles, letters and diagrams suitable for intermediate level of supervision and operations. The high level includes the ability to write a number of complex work documents and, if needed, provide informal and summary translations but are not intended to reflect the skills of a professional translator.

The tourism English competency unit in accordance with the SKKNI above can be applied to the entire tourism sector and includes oral communication skills, reading and writing in English at the basic operational level. Examples of oral competency topics for tourism English competence include; welcome, say thank you and say goodbye to customers and colleagues, answer requests, provide factual information, communicate via telephone and face to face. Other examples of transacting using simple tourism English or providing assistance include; buy souvenirs, pay restaurant or hotel bills, pay for travel services, provide directions, schedules and other arrangements, choose a meal menu, help check entry and exit procedures, and provide time-related advice.

Tourism destination where the English language for tourism includes; facilities, local attractions, areas of interest, shopping locations, tour registration locations, pick-up and drop-off for tours, bus terminals, taxis, and transportation services. Other information on the location of tourist destinations includes; opening and closing hours, tour procedures, exchange of money and exchange rates, prices and fees, room and floor numbers, safety regulations, travel guides, dictionaries, brochures, menus and maps.

4. Conclusion

The quality of e-module tourism based on learners and context is one of a component of successful learning instruction. It could be designed by considering learner's needs and context or stakeholder's needs (tourism industry and government). Tour and travel companies, hotels and restaurants really need human resources who able to communicate English for tourism very well both in spoken and written. The problems of English for tourism based on SKKNI (Indonesian national standard working competencies) commonly in speaking skills, listening skills, reading skills and writing skills. While specific problems of English competences which identified by researchers are writing and sending email and faxes, making on-line ticketing, browsing the internet, making online hotel booking and offering destination guides, elaborate written documents such as letters or budgets, telephone conversations, make presentations to audiences, attend fairs and conferences and understand all types of written information on tourist destinations.

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Research and development (R&D) electronic modules (e-modules) learning English based on learners and context-based tourism aims to help solve problems of mastery and improvement of English, especially for tourism for students of the Lampung State Polytechnic Tourism Study Program (Polinela) and tourism sector stakeholders in general. This research and development requires seriousness, innovation and creativity in packaging English language materials for tourism. Realizing quality research results that have benefits and contributions in the tourism sector certainly requires assistance and support from various parties. Thanks to the Promoter Prof. Dr. Basuki Wibawa, M.Pd. and Co promoter Prof. Dr. Syarif Sumantri, M.Pd. who have guided and provided input, suggestions,

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